

Unaffordable housing and mental health: a longitudinal analysis using the UK Household Longitudinal Study

University of Bath – B.Sc. Economics

Elliot Arévalo

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Abstract

This paper analyses the impact of unaffordable housing on mental health in the United Kingdom using longitudinal data from the UK Household Longitudinal Study. I estimate a fixed effects regression by ordinary least squares and find that, on average, housing becoming unaffordable is associated with a decrease in individuals' mental health score (SF-12 MCS) of 0.567 points relative to housing remaining affordable. Further longitudinal evidence indicates that, on average, this association is strongest among individuals who spent two consecutive years in unaffordable housing and becomes insignificant after an additional year. These findings provide important evidence for policymakers to be able to consider the full costs and benefits of both housing affordability and mental health interventions.

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I. Introduction

Housing affordability in the UK has been falling over the last decade as growth in house sales and rental prices has outpaced growth in household incomes (ONS, 2023b, 2024), to the extent that, taking into account housing quality and purchasing power, the UK has the highest price of housing of any developed economy (Corlett and Judge, 2024). Shortages in the supply of housing, driven by a complex and unpredictable planning system and overreliance on speculative private development (CMA, 2024), have been significant drivers of rising costs. Foreign investment has also been recognised as an important driver of house prices (Sá, 2016) and led to the introduction of a new tax on foreign home buyers in 2021 (HMRC, 2021). The decline in housing subsidies has also been recognised as an important determinant of falling housing affordability, especially among lower-income households (Mulheirn, Browne and Tsoukalis, 2023).

Unaffordable housing disproportionately affects lower-income households as they dedicate higher proportions of their incomes to housing costs. The falling stock of social housing, down by over 1.5 million since 1980, has increasingly forced lower-income households into the private rental market (Shelter, 2019). Successive four-year freezes of Local Housing Allowance (LHA) from 2016 to 2020 and 2020 to 2024 meant that LHA only covered 1 in 20 rental properties on Zoopla in 2023 (Waters and Wernham, 2023). Failing social safety nets have left lower-income households exposed, with private renters spending a third of their income on rent in 2022 (DLUHC, 2023) above the 30% affordability threshold used by the UK Office for National Statistics (ONS; 2023b). Lower-priced rents are less affordable for lower-income households than median-priced rents for median-income households (ONS, 2023b). In recognition of the detrimental effects of unaffordable housing, the UK Government uprated LHA to 30% of local rental market rates in April 2024 (DWP, 2024).

This study explores the impact of unaffordable housing on mental health, contributing to a nascent body of literature that has examined outcomes among several higher-income countries and identified evidence that suggests that the experience of unaffordable housing stress has a negative impact on self-reported mental health.

I employ longitudinal data from 2009 to 2023 from the UK Household Longitudinal Study (UKHLS; University of Essex, IESR, 2023), also known as Understanding Society, a comprehensive panel survey that covers domains of family and social ties, employment,

education, financial resources and health. It makes use of probability weights to account for sample attrition, non-response and unequal selection probabilities, as well as facilitate population inference (IESR, 2023).

The primary outcome variable is individuals' mental health as measured by the Mental Component Summary (MCS) score of the 12-Item Short Form (SF-12) questionnaire (Ware, Kosinski and Keller, 1996). It has been validated for use in the UK general population (Gandek et al., 1998; Jenkinson et al., 1997), is robust to retesting and is a strong predictor of the presence of depressive disorders (Ware, Kosinski and Keller, 1996).

The primary treatment variable indicates whether someone is in unaffordable housing or not depending on whether an individual dedicates more than 30% of their household disposable income to housing costs and their household belongs to the bottom 40% of the equivalised disposable income distribution. This definition is denoted as the 30/40 rule (Nepal, Tanton and Harding, 2010) and has been used widely across similar studies (Bentley, Baker and Mason, 2012; Baker, Mason and Bentley, 2015; Baker et al., 2020; Arundel et al., 2022).

Bringing these elements together and including a vector of control variables, I conduct a fixed effects regression using ordinary least squares (OLS) and find that, on average, housing becoming unaffordable is associated with a decrease in individuals' mental health score of 0.567 points relative to housing remaining affordable. The magnitude of this baseline result is equivalent to 29% of the effect of becoming unemployed on mental health (from Paul and Moser, 2009) and implies a 16% increase in the proportion of people with 30-day depressive disorders¹.

Additional longitudinal evidence indicates that the negative effect of being in unaffordable housing on mental health is above average for those who stay in unaffordable housing for shorter periods of time. For those who were in unaffordable housing for a maximum of two consecutive waves during the sampling period, the impact on mental health was almost double that of the baseline result. Meanwhile, the association with mental health becomes insignificant for those who spent a maximum of three consecutive waves in unaffordable housing. The

¹ This result predicts the presence of depressive disorders using SF-12 MCS cut-off scores. These cut-offs rely on the assumption that the share of those with depressive disorders in the UK is the same as the European average.

robustness of this result is confirmed by estimating the event-study estimator from de Chaisemartin and D'Haultfœuille (2024).

The strength of the 30/40 approach in defining unaffordable housing is verified by comparing its estimated coefficient to those estimated by the 30/60m and residual approaches to defining unaffordable housing. The 30/60m rule considers those who spend more than 30% of their income on housing costs and whose income is below 60% of the national median income as being in unaffordable housing, while the residual approach considers income after housing costs against the Minimum Income Standards (MIS). The MIS are income thresholds at which a household is deemed to meet a minimum acceptable standard of living as defined by the Centre for Research in Social Policy at the University of Loughborough (2023) for the 11 most common household types. The association between unaffordable housing, as defined by the 30/60m rule, on mental health is slightly larger than that estimated with the 30/40 rule, but is not statistically different, suggesting that income is not an important driver of treatment effect heterogeneity. Conversely, unaffordable housing as defined by the residual approach is not significantly associated with mental health, likely because it captures a wider variety of individuals.

In summary, this study analyses UK panel data from 2009 to 2023 using a fixed effects regression to explore how the association between being in unaffordable housing and mental health varies across ratio and residual definitions of unaffordable housing and across the duration of exposure to unaffordable housing, providing a unique contribution to the existing literature.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: section II reviews the relevant literature; section III describes the data used, defines the variables of interest and introduces the empirical methodology; section IV presents summary statistics, baseline results, further complementary findings, as well as limitations; and finally, section V provides concluding remarks and implications for policy.

II. Literature review

Unaffordable housing may have a negative impact on mental health, but research in this field is still emerging. In contrast, the influence of housing conditions on mental health is more well established. Namely, living in substandard, temporary housing has a strong association with

negative mental health outcomes (Bonney, 2007; Pevalin et al., 2017), whether stemming from overcrowding, social isolation (Evans, Wells and Moch, 2003) or increased exposure to dampness and mould, harmful chemicals, thermal stress, among other factors (Krieger and Higgins, 2002; Shaw, 2004). However, the body of research on how housing affordability problems affect mental health is still developing, with a consensus beginning to emerge.

A. Mechanisms

Housing affordability captures the relationship between people and housing (Stone, 2006). Financial insecurities related to housing are important social determinants of mental health, especially in advanced economies that have observed increased living standards over time (Cohen, Farley and Mason, 2003; Singh et al., 2019). The home reflects identity, allows individuals to exercise control and provides security, offering protection against not only the elements but also negative social conditions (Evans, Wells and Moch, 2003). Downing (2016) outlines stress, effect-budgeting, frustration-aggression and trust as the pathways by which housing unaffordability exerts its influence on mental health. Stress is brought about by the financial burden of rent or a mortgage, especially for households on lower incomes or in unstable employment (Fitch et al., 2011; Richardson, Elliott and Roberts, 2013), illustrated by Sen's (1992) insight that "relative deprivation in the space of incomes can yield absolute deprivation in the space of capabilities". In more severe situations, the risk of eviction or repossession causes feelings of guilt, anxiety and shame (Ross and Squires, 2011). The impact of unaffordable housing is also reflected in reduced availability of time and resources to dedicate to health-promoting behaviours, including exercise, socialising and eating healthily (Freeman, 2002). Individuals may also experience frustration-aggression when their cultural expectations, prevalent in advanced economies, of being rewarded for their work and having access to affordable housing or homeownership, remain unmet. This effect may be mediated by an individual's coping mechanisms, personal capabilities and the emotional or informational social support offered by others (WHO and CGF, 2014). Finally, being in unaffordable housing disrupts people's ontological security, or sense of trust in the way their worlds are ordered (Dupuis and Thomas, 1998). A home creates a constant space where routines are performed independent of the scrutiny of others, setting up a secure base around which the resident can establish their identity. A disturbance in the security of maintaining that space can have a corresponding effect on an individual's personal sense of security.

B. Housing affordability

Defining and measuring housing affordability is a challenging task, as it involves synthesising the “subjective social and material experience of people in relation to their individual housing situations” (Stone, 2006), bringing diverse realities under single definitions. Most studies in the housing affordability and mental health literature adopt a normative approach in their characterisation of affordability. This involves establishing a threshold value for the limit or norm of housing affordability, as opposed to relying on survey respondents’ evaluations of the affordability of their housing, as in the subjective approach (Li, 2015). Taylor, Pevalin and Todd (2007) utilise the latter approach and analyse responses to a question posed to heads of households about whether they had struggled to pay for housing over the previous 12 months.

The most common normative approach is the housing costs to income measure, which expresses housing costs as a share of total income. The 30% threshold, where households spending more than 30% of their income on housing are deemed to be in unaffordable housing, is used widely by researchers, banks and government departments, including the UK’s ONS (2023b), as a robust measure of affordability (Rea et al., 2008). It is recognised for its practicality, comparability and ease of understanding. Thresholds between 25 to 30% have been found to be consistent with lender ratios for qualifying for a mortgage loan (Borrowman, Kazakevitch and Frost, 2017), being unable to afford an additional bedroom to house a child (Affordable Housing Commission, 2019) and material hardship (Bramley, 2012; Meen, 2018). A national survey carried out by the UK Affordable Housing Commission (AHC; 2019) suggests a strong link between high housing costs to income ratios and financial stress, showing, for example, that covering the price of food and basic items becomes more difficult as housing costs increase relative to income.

The 30% rule is not without its shortcomings as a measure of housing costs relative to income. There is a strong likelihood that it classifies someone not in financial stress as being subject to housing unaffordability as it does not differentiate between high-income households that choose to spend large proportions of their income on housing and lower-income households who are forced to (Stone, 2006; Kutty, 2005). Additionally, the AHC (2019) finds that failing to adjust for the number of children in a household leads to underestimates of the proportion of households with affordability problems.

To account for these measurement issues, different complementary approaches have been advocated for. One of these involves adjusting household income so that it takes into account household size and composition. The most common approach for doing so divides household income by the household's corresponding OECD-modified equivalence scale (2015) that assigns a value of 1 to the household head, 0.5 to each additional adult and 0.3 to each child. In order to ensure the same share of income spent on housing represents an equivalent financial burden for households, Nepal, Tanton and Harding (2010) limit the variation in incomes by combining the 30% threshold with a second condition that only includes households in the bottom 40% of the equivalised income distribution. Bentley et al. (2011) show that high-income households that choose to dedicate more than 30% of their income to housing suffer no negative impact on mental health. Therefore, the 30/40 rule builds on the strengths of the 30% rule while more accurately including those who truly experience housing affordability stress. It is also less sensitive than the 30% rule to whether gross or disposable household income measures are used. A similar approach promoted by Meen (2018) weights a measure of housing costs relative to income by income quintile to take into account that lower-income households are disproportionately more likely to face housing affordability stress than higher-income households.

Ratios of housing costs to income are subject to limitations. There exists a degree of arbitrariness when dictating where to establish the cut-off for when a household is in unaffordable housing (Hulchanski, 1995), although, as discussed above, the 30% threshold is based on reasoned considerations rather than being haphazardly determined (Nepal, Tanton and Harding, 2010). Inevitably, it is likely that households directly on either side of any threshold will be quite similar. Other critiques highlight that the ratio approach may obscure underconsumption of housing, where a household lives in substandard but affordable housing, or other responses to high housing costs, such as an individual living with their parents for longer than they would have intended or desired (AHC, 2019). Furthermore, the ratio approach does not adequately take into account whether the level of income after housing costs is enough (Jewkes and Delgadillo, 2010; Borrowman, Kazakevitch and Frost, 2015). For example, a lower-income household's ability to pay for non-housing necessities may be significantly impaired when spending only 20% of their income on housing.

Stone (2006) proposes an alternative to the ratio approach. The residual approach compares income after housing costs against an income threshold that reflects the cost of a minimum

basket of goods, capturing the struggles a lower-income household spending 20% of their income on housing costs faces. A household whose income after housing costs is below the income threshold is classed as being in unaffordable housing. It more accurately reflects whether a household can meet its non-housing needs within its income constraint (Jewkes and Delgadillo, 2010), factoring in the differential distributional impact of housing costs (AHC, 2019). It also factors in changes in household composition as income thresholds are constructed for different household types.

The challenges around the residual approach consist of defining the income thresholds at which households no longer have enough income to cover their basic needs. Primarily, the availability of income thresholds within the context a researcher is working in may be an issue; using the ratio approach may be more straightforward. Should income thresholds exist within the relevant context, the question of what constitutes a minimum basket of goods may generate disagreement and will influence who is determined to be in unaffordable housing. There also exists an element of arbitrariness in establishing the income thresholds, as with the ratio approach, such that households directly above or below the cut-off will be quite similar.

Both ratio and residual measures capture housing affordability at points in time, limiting their abilities to factor in how individuals may slip in and out of affordability over time. Temporary experiences of being in unaffordable housing differ from permanent ones (Rowley and Ong, 2012; Baker, Mason and Bentley, 2015), so repeated measurement over time is necessary to fully capture the effect of unaffordable housing on individuals.

Ultimately, the assessment and measurement of housing affordability requires a nuanced perspective that takes into account the relative strengths and weaknesses of the available approaches.

C. Housing affordability and mental health

The role of unaffordable housing as a determinant of mental health has received recent attention, particularly in higher-income countries, including the United Kingdom (Taylor, Pevalin and Todd, 2007; Bentley et al., 2016; Reeves et al., 2016; Dotsikas et al., 2023), Australia (Bentley et al., 2011, 2016; Bentley, Baker and Mason, 2012; Mason et al., 2013; Baker, Mason and Bentley, 2015; Bentley, Baker and Aitken, 2019; Baker et al., 2020), United States (Pollack, Griffin and Lynch, 2010; Newman and Holupka, 2015; Kuroki, 2023), Hong Kong (Chung et al., 2020) and Netherlands (Arundel et al., 2022), with the consensus

suggesting the experience of unaffordable housing may have a negative impact on self-reported mental health.

Taylor, Pevalin and Todd (2007) analyse data from the British Household Panel Survey (BHPS) from 1991 to 2003 to estimate whether heads of household who reported having problems paying for their housing in the previous 12 months experienced a decline in their mental health, as given by their score on the 12-item General Health Questionnaire. Their sample excludes observations for respondents who did not have any housing costs, implying their estimates yield an approximation of the average treatment effect on the treated (ATT) as opposed to the average treatment effect (ATE). Controlling for the impact of negative financial events and other covariates on mental health, they find housing payment problems have a negative impact on the mental health of heads of households over and above those associated with general financial hardship, equivalent to the effect of marital breakdown or job loss. Their analysis also controls for the effect of unobserved, time-invariant individual-specific characteristics on mental health by using a fixed effects regression with year dummies, effectively estimating a two-way fixed effects (TWFE) model.

Their use of a TWFE regression may produce biased estimates. Recent findings highlight that TWFE estimation only delivers consistent estimates of average treatment effects under strong assumptions about homogeneity in treatment effects between groups and over time (De Chaisemartin and D'Haultfœuille, 2020; Borusyak, Jaravel, and Spiess, 2021; Callaway and Sant'Anna 2021; Goodman-Bacon 2021; Sun and Abraham 2021) and linear additive effects between individual-specific and time-specific confounders (Imai and Kim, 2021). The former fails to hold when newly treated units are compared to already treated units and there is heterogeneity in the treatment effect across time; in other words, if the effect of being in unaffordable housing on mental health diminishes over time, then TWFE will estimate positive weights (in contrast to the negative expected effect of housing unaffordability on mental health). However, there exists the small possibility that treatment effect heterogeneity may be limited or idiosyncratic, yielding consistent estimates.

Bentley et al. (2011) use fixed effects regression to analyse data from participants in the Australian Household, Income, and Labour Dynamics survey from 2001 to 2007. They find that among individuals in lower-income households, entering unaffordable housing was associated with a decrease in their mental health score after controlling for changes in

equivalised household income and moving house, identifying an approximation of the ATE across households in the bottom 40% of the income distribution. The mental health of individuals in high-income households did not suffer when in unaffordable housing, as defined by the 30% rule. This study makes use of the Mental Component Summary (MCS) of the Short-Form 36 (SF-36) questionnaire to record mental health status, a widely used self-completion measure.

Baker and coauthors (2020) use a longitudinal regression with Mundlak adjustment to examine the effect on mental health of prolonged exposure to unaffordable housing. This model allows them to capture within and between-person differences. Over three 5-year windows, they differentiate between those who remain in and those who slip in and out of unaffordable housing and find that both prolonged and intermittent exposure are associated with lower levels of mental health. This effect is robust to the inclusion of a number of control variables, but the magnitude of the effect is slightly reduced when accounting for respondents' baseline level of mental health.

These three studies may not sufficiently account for the inherently unobservable anticipation effect of entering unaffordable housing, where individuals pre-empt the effects of entering into housing unaffordability during a time of anticipated hardship, whether on a macroeconomic or individual level, leading their level of mental health to fall before they are recorded as being in unaffordable housing in the data and an underestimation of the effect of unaffordable housing on mental health.

Reeves et al. (2016) exploit the quasi-natural experiment created by the UK government's April 2011 reduction in financial support for lower-income households in the private rental sector (LHA). They adopt a difference-in-difference approach and find that the prevalence of depressive symptoms among private renters receiving LHA increased relative to those who were not receiving LHA. This study's design exploits an exogenous change in policy, meaning the result is more likely to represent a causal estimate. However, the result may be limited by lower external validity than the longitudinal studies due to its estimation of an ATT.

Therefore, in light of the emerging consensus in the literature on the effect of being in unaffordable housing on mental health, this study provides an original contribution by analysing UK panel data from 2009 to 2023 using a fixed effects regression, investigating how the average association between unaffordable housing and mental health varies across ratio and

residual definitions of unaffordable housing and across different lengths of exposure to unaffordable housing.

III. Data and empirical methodology

A. Data

This study utilises the UK Household Longitudinal Study (UKHLS; University of Essex, IESR, 2023), or Understanding Society, a longitudinal household panel survey that began in 2009, interviewing around 40,000 households across the UK at the baseline year. The study sample was selected using a stratified, clustered equal probability sample design to make it nationally representative (IESR, 2023). Individuals found in the initial representative sample and their household members are re-interviewed 12 months apart, while data collection for each wave occurs over two years. Responses are collated across individuals and households and pertain to questions in the domains of family and social ties, employment, education, financial resources and health.

Data for this study came from responses merged across Waves 1 (2009 to 2011) to 13 (2021 to 2023). After 13 survey waves, the General Population Sample lost 65% of the initial wave respondents, with the greatest attrition occurring among young people, those from an ethnic minority background and those on lower incomes or with no qualifications (Cabrera-Alvarez and Lynn, 2023). The application of inverse probability weights, also known as sampling or design weights, accounted for unequal selection probabilities, adjusted for differential nonresponse and attrition, and facilitated population inference. However, some subgroups, such as people with lower incomes, were slightly underrepresented even after the application of probability weights.

After filtering out missing responses for the primary variables of interest, the unweighted sample for analysis consisted of 268,233 observations across 27,849 individuals, rendering the panel unbalanced.

B. Outcome variable

The MCS score of the 12-Item Short-Form (SF-12) Health Survey was used as the primary outcome variable measure for the analysis. A more succinct version of its 36-item counterpart, it has been shown to closely mirror scores from the SF-36 while exerting a lower burden on the respondent (Ware, Kosinski and Keller, 1996; Jenkinson and Layte, 1997). It has been

validated for use across various populations (Sanderson and Andrews, 2002; Vilagut et al., 2008; Wee, Davis and Hamel, 2008), including the UK general population (Gandek et al., 1998; Jenkinson et al., 1997), and is robust to retest effects such that it can detect within-person changes in mental health over time (Hemingway et al., 1997).

The MCS draws from 4 subscales on the self-completion questionnaire that cover vitality, social functioning, role limitations due to emotional problems (role-emotional) and mental health. The score ranges from 0 to 100, with higher values indicating better mental health, and is designed to have a mean of 50 and standard deviation of 10 among the general United States population (Ware, Kosinski and Keller, 1995). For the analytical sample weighted to represent the population, the mean SF-12 MCS score was 48.72 with a standard deviation of 10.36, which closely approximates the estimates observed in the American population.

Self-reported measures of mental health suffer from limitations caused by measurement error due to recall bias, lack of incentives or social image concerns (Braghieri, Levy and Makarin, 2022). In addition, they rely on the implicit assumption that respondents treat response scales in the same way (Benjamin et al., 2023). However, these are assumed to occur in a random manner and are the current best practice in the domain of mental health (Chan, 2010). The SF-12 MCS remains a proven screening tool for detecting depression and anxiety disorders.

C. Treatment variables

The primary treatment variable defines an individual as being in unaffordable housing according to the 30/40 rule, when a household spends more than 30% of its disposable income on housing costs and the household belongs to the bottom 40% of the equivalised disposable income distribution, as defined by Nepal, Tanton and Harding (2010) and implemented across similar studies (Bentley, Baker and Mason, 2012; Baker, Mason and Bentley, 2015; Baker et al., 2020; Arundel et al., 2022). Income is equivalised according to the OECD modified equivalence scales and the 40th percentile of the income distribution was calculated using weighted sample estimates. UKHLS household income variables are reliable population-level indicators, serving as the primary data source used by the Department for Work and Pensions for official UK statistics on income dynamics (IESR, 2023). Where the definition of unaffordable housing is not specified in the analysis, this definition is utilised.

Two alternative definitions of unaffordable housing are also considered. The first adopts a similar approach to the 30/40 rule but instead of defining those on lower incomes as the bottom

40% of the income distribution, it uses the UK government's more stringent definition for those in relative low income where net equivalised disposable income is less than 60% of the UK median income (DWP, 2023). This is denominated the "30/60m" rule.

The second alternative adopts a residual income approach as advocated by Stone (2006). This approach compares household disposable incomes to a given income threshold at which a household is deemed to meet a minimum acceptable standard of living. The Centre for Research in Social Policy at the University of Loughborough (2023) have defined the MIS for the 11 most common household types going back to 2008. The MIS is widely used in other incomes research, with users ranging from the Living Wage Foundation, the Scottish Government and various charities. It is based on what members of the UK public think is needed for a minimum acceptable standard of living at which individuals feel like they can take part in society and live with dignity without feeling excluded. Creating a customised threshold for each of the most common household types allows the MIS to overcome the limitations of using standard equivalisation scales. These consider average elasticities across individuals at all income levels and may underestimate the relative cost of each additional child or the costs of maintaining a lone parent family compared to a couple family (Hirsch et al., 2020). This approach also benefits from the strengths of all residual approaches to defining unaffordable housing; namely, accounting for whether a household's level of income after housing costs is enough to cover non-housing essential needs while accounting for changes in household composition.

D. Identification strategy

Using a fixed effects estimator is a common strategy when working with panel data. Fixed effects models define the explanatory variables as deviations from their individual means across all available survey waves. This approach allows for arbitrary correlation between factors that drive unobserved, time-invariant variation between individuals and the observed explanatory variables (Wooldridge, 2007). Mental health is systematically influenced by unobserved, time-invariant psychological characteristics (DeNeve and Cooper, 1999); therefore, fixed effects are preferred to random effects to remove any variation in mental health levels between individuals. This intuition is confirmed by the results from the Hausman test that assesses whether individual characteristics are correlated with the explanatory variables.

As a baseline specification, I estimate the following fixed effects regression model:

$$MH_{it} = \beta \times UH_{it} + \mathbf{X}_i\gamma + \alpha_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

where MH_{it} represents individual i 's level of mental health given by their SF-12 MCS score at survey wave t ; UH_{it} is a binary variable that indicates whether an individual i was in unaffordable housing during survey wave t ; \mathbf{X}_i is a vector of individual-level controls; and α_i is an individual-specific error term that captures the unobserved, time-invariant heterogeneity between individuals, while ε_{it} is an idiosyncratic error term that varies across individuals and over time.

I estimate equation (1) by ordinary least squares (OLS) using standard errors clustered at the primary sampling unit level and applying probability weights. Clustered standard errors and probability weights achieve more consistent estimates by accounting for clustered sampling of the population (IESR, 2023) and correcting for endogenous sampling. They also correct for serial correlation by allowing for arbitrary correlation and changing variances within each cluster, making the estimator more efficient (Wooldridge, 2007), although serial correlation and cross-sectional dependence are less likely to be issues in micro panels (Baltagi, 2021). Finally, they are able to correct for the presence of heteroscedasticity in the variation of the idiosyncratic error term and identify average partial effects in the presence of heterogeneous treatment effects (Abadie et al., 2023; Solon, Haider and Wooldridge, 2015).

To ensure that the fixed effects estimator yields consistent estimates, a vector of control variables is included to complement the fixed effects mechanism in addressing concerns about endogeneity stemming from omitted variable bias and reverse causality. The influence of potential time-varying confounders that can exert an influence on both mental health and housing affordability is accounted for, including equivalised household disposable income, International Labour Organization (ILO) labour force status, household size and composition, age, age squared, a dummy for whether the individual changed address since the previous wave, the Physical Component Summary score from the SF-12, the regional unemployment rate, marital status and housing tenure. The regional unemployment rate (ONS, 2023a) was included as a control for regional time-varying macroeconomic conditions that may affect individuals' mental health and affect housing affordability.

Other controls that were considered but did not have an effect on the effect of unaffordable housing on mental health include region of residence, council tax band, a dummy for whether the interview took place during Covid-19, a dummy for whether a person suffers from a long-term health condition or disability, a dummy for whether the individual was the household representative and a dummy for whether the person had become divorced, separated or widowed since the previous wave.

Individual lags of SF-12 MCS score were also included as a control to account for potential issues of reverse causality. Those who suffer from pre-existing mental health conditions are more likely to have reduced income and employment (WHO, 2014), implying they are also more likely to be in unaffordable housing. This is an issue if individuals with pre-existing mental health conditions experience greater deviations from their mean mental health score when they are in unaffordable housing than those without mental health conditions, as the change in mental health from being in unaffordable housing may partially reflect the effect of the pre-existing mental health condition and be overestimated. Including the lagged mental health score mitigated against baseline differences in mental health status before entering unaffordable housing. Two measures of indicators of depression were also considered as covariates but were omitted in the final specification. Lagged dummy variables that indicate whether an individual's SF-12 MCS score was below the cut-offs consistent with diagnoses of 30-day and 12-month depressive disorders were not included because their inclusion did not make a difference to the result of interest. These cut-offs are described in greater detail in the 'Baseline results' section. A different variable that directly captured whether respondents had been diagnosed with depression had insufficient observations for estimation.

The lag of the unaffordable housing dummy is also incorporated to isolate the effect on mental health of entering unaffordable housing, as the interpretation of β relies on holding all other variables *ceteris paribus*, such that the individual cannot have been in unaffordable housing in the previous wave.

Therefore, estimating the coefficient of interest β from equation (1) identifies the association between entering unaffordable housing and an individual's mental health score, on average, relative to remaining in affordable housing.

IV. Results

A. Descriptive statistics

Just under 8% of all observations (across individuals and time) were in unaffordable housing over the sampling period. Over 28% of all individuals entered unaffordable housing for at least one period, while under 1% of individuals were in unaffordable housing across all surveyed waves.

Those in unaffordable housing had an average mental health score that was over 3 points lower than those in affordable housing, as presented in Table 1. Furthermore, across all population characteristics considered, those exposed to unaffordable housing always had a lower mean mental health than their counterparts in affordable housing. The gap in average mental health between those in unaffordable and affordable housing was particularly notable among the economically inactive and those with a long-standing health condition or disability. Above average gaps also existed for those with no degree, those who had moved since the previous survey wave, those in the 45 to 54 age group and those in the 55 to 64 age group. Those in unaffordable housing who were unemployed or had a long-standing health condition or disability had the lowest average levels of mental health.

Table A.1 displays further information about the characteristics of the pooled analytical sample broken down by the affordability of housing. It shows that those in unaffordable housing are more likely to be in precarious employment, family and housing tenure situations relative to those in affordable housing. They are five times more likely to be unemployed, six times more likely to be privately renting and four times more likely to be in social housing. They are also over twice as likely to be separated, divorced or widowed; to have moved house since the previous wave; or be from a minority ethnic group background.

Moreover, those in unaffordable housing tend to be younger, but as Table 1 shows, older people in unaffordable housing tend to suffer a greater negative effect on their mental health relative to their counterparts in affordable housing than younger people. Finally, among households in unaffordable housing, there tend to be less adults per child, likely indicating a greater incidence of single-parent households.

Table 1: Summary statistics for the SF-12 MCS score by affordability of housing

Variable	In unaffordable housing			In affordable housing		
	Mean	SD	n	Mean	SD	n
Full sample	46.07	(11.51)	20,715	49.29	(9.94)	247,518
Sex						
Male	47.35	(11.04)	8,124	50.57	(9.31)	107,750
Female	45.24	(11.73)	12,591	48.30	(10.29)	139,768
Age cohort						
16-24	44.84	(12.02)	2,917	46.38	(11.25)	22,037
25-34	45.13	(11.24)	3,694	47.03	(10.33)	30,967
35-44	45.71	(11.19)	4,527	47.98	(9.80)	43,038
45-54	44.89	(11.74)	4,185	48.81	(9.76)	51,423
55-64	46.99	(11.51)	3,084	50.55	(9.46)	48,430
65+	51.06	(9.92)	2,080	52.50	(8.66)	48,983
Marital status						
Married/de facto	47.57	(10.57)	9,002	50.00	(9.32)	173,726
Sep./widow./divorced	45.76	(12.29)	4,750	48.86	(10.74)	29,331
Never married	44.33	(11.87)	6,870	46.79	(11.25)	43,974
Labour force status						
Employed	47.38	(10.31)	10,490	49.25	(9.35)	152,554
Unemployed	42.79	(12.41)	2,614	44.19	(12.26)	6,994
Inactive	45.39	(12.43)	7,601	49.76	(10.60)	87,878
Long-standing health condition or disability						
Yes	42.40	(12.81)	7,500	47.27	(11.51)	82,094
No	48.15	(10.12)	13,215	50.29	(8.89)	165,424
Education: has a degree						
Yes	46.64	(10.68)	4,564	49.25	(9.29)	75,619
No	45.91	(11.72)	16,151	49.31	(10.22)	171,899
Changed address in the last year						
Yes	44.37	(11.95)	2,190	47.77	(10.24)	10,716
No	46.03	(11.49)	15,831	49.15	(10.03)	208,930

Notes: This table presents SF-12 Mental Component Summary score summary statistics by whether an individual's housing was affordable. Figures are estimated using the unweighted pooled analytical sample.

B. Baseline results

Table 2 presents estimates of β in equation (1) on the SF-12 MCS score and shows that being in unaffordable housing had a small but statistically significant negative impact on people's mental health. The first column shows results for the simplest specification that only included individual fixed effects on top of the treatment and outcome variables. The second column, my

preferred specification, includes a vector of control variables as well as individual fixed effects. Finally, in the third column, survey wave fixed effects are also included that rely on greater assumptions. The results are relatively stable across all specifications, but the point estimates for the specifications with control variables are smaller in magnitude relative to the one without, while remaining significant at the 1% level. This smaller magnitude of estimates in the presence of covariates is to be expected, as they control for circumstances associated with decreases in mental health.

The coefficient on my preferred specification that includes individual fixed effects and control variables indicates that entering unaffordable housing is associated with a decrease in individuals' mental health score of 0.567 points relative to remaining in affordable housing.

The coefficient from the specification in column (3) uses two-way fixed effects and is the result of isolating the variation within each individual and within each survey wave. It is very similar in magnitude to the coefficient from the preferred specification. This similarity suggests, in the absence of bias from heterogeneity in treatment effects and nonlinear combinations of the individual-specific and survey wave-specific confounders, that the effect of any year-specific influences on all individuals' mental health and housing affordability is minimal. These biases are mitigated against by the inclusion of control variables, such as lags of the outcome and treatment variables, and the application of clustered standard errors and probability weights.

Table 2: Baseline results, SF-12 MCS score

	SF-12 MCS score		
	(1)	(2)	(3)
In unaffordable housing	-0.742 ^{***} (0.193)	-0.567 ^{***} (0.201)	-0.582 ^{***} (0.200)
Observations	95,699	79,176	79,176
Individual fixed effects	✓	✓	✓
Controls		✓	✓
Survey wave fixed effects			✓

Notes: This table explores the effect of entering unaffordable housing on individuals' mental health. It presents estimates of coefficient β from equation (1) with the SF-12 Mental Component Summary score as the outcome variable. Column 1 estimates equation (1) only including individual fixed effects; column 2, the preferred specification, also includes controls; column 3 also incorporates survey wave fixed effects. Standard errors in brackets are clustered at primary sampling unit level and ^{***} $p < 0.01$. Full results for the preferred specification are available in Table A.2.

To help understand the magnitude of the baseline effect and provide intuition for the practical significance of the results from the preferred specification, a few benchmarks for comparison are provided. First, 18% of the difference between the average SF-12 MCS scores for those in affordable versus unaffordable housing (3.22; see Table 1) is attributable to being in unaffordable housing, with the rest of the variation coming from the control variables. Second, the effect is equivalent to a 0.05 standard deviation unit change relative to the standard deviation population mental health score of 10.36. Third, the magnitude of the effect is benchmarked to equivalent effects of entering unemployment and becoming separated, divorced or widowed. Relative to effects estimated using equation (1), entering unaffordable housing has 47% of the effect on mental health that becoming separated, divorced or widowed does and 37% of the effect on mental health that becoming unemployed does. Using a comparable estimate from a meta-analysis by Paul and Moser (2009) that looks at the effect of moving from employment into unemployment using longitudinal data, entering unaffordable housing has 29% of the effect of becoming unemployed on mental health.

As a final benchmark, I assess the number of additional people who fell under the SF-12 MCS optimal cut-off score for detecting the presence of depressive disorders. Despite the establishment of cut-offs for the SF-12 MCS in the United States (Ware, Kosinski and Keller, 1994; Ware and Gandek, 1998), European (Vilagut et al., 2013) and Australian (Gill et al., 2007) general populations, an equivalent cut-off for the UK population has not been identified in the existing literature. Therefore, it is assumed that the share of those with depressive disorders, as identified by the SF-12 MCS cut-off, is the same as the average share of those with depressive disorders across Europe obtained by Vilagut and coauthors (2013). They calculate the average proportions from their stratified, multistage, clustered area probability sample of the adult population in Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, The Netherlands, and Spain, differentiating between those who had depressive disorders in the previous 30 days versus the previous 12 months. Using the optimal SF-36 MCS (highly comparable long form version of the SF-12) cut-off points, they find that the SF-12 predicted that 13.5% of the population had a depressive disorder within the previous 30 days and (with slightly less precision) that 19.5% of the population had a depressive disorder within the previous 12 months. These same proportions are translated over to the weighted Understanding Society sample to obtain SF-12 MCS cut-offs of 40.60 for 12-month disorders and 36.76 for 30-day disorders. By changing the outcome variable to a dummy for whether an individual was above or below these cut-offs but

maintaining the preferred specification, the change in the proportion of people who suffer from depressive disorders due to entering unaffordable housing was estimated. Entering unaffordable housing was associated with a 2.1 percentage point (16%) increase in the proportion of people with 30-day depressive disorders and was not significantly related to change in the proportion of people with 12-month depressive disorders (see Table A.3).

C. Variation by number of consecutive years in unaffordable housing

How the effect of unaffordable housing on mental health varies by the number of consecutive waves spent in unaffordable housing is also explored. Given that someone was in unaffordable housing for at least one wave during the sampling period, the average number of years spent in unaffordable housing was 2.6. Unaffordable housing tended to be relatively sticky; individuals in unaffordable housing during one period left unaffordable housing the next year approximately 50% of the time. However, given that an individual's housing was affordable in one year, their housing was only unaffordable the next period 4% of the time.

The analysis focuses on those who spent a maximum of one consecutive year (group 1), a maximum of two consecutive years (group 2) and a maximum of at least three consecutive years (group 3) in unaffordable housing over the sampling period. The differences in the characteristics of these different groups are presented in Table A.4. Among all three groups, equivalised household incomes are similar but the circumstances in which the individuals in each group find themselves differ. Those in groups 1 and 2 are more similar, with those in group 2 slightly more likely to be in social housing or the private rental sector and less likely to have a mortgage, but few other significant differences. However, those in group 3 are much more likely to be older individuals in the 55 to 64 and 65 plus age groups; economically inactive; separated, divorced or widowed; and living in social housing or the private rental sector.

Table 3 presents estimates of β in equation (1) on the SF-12 MCS score for groups 1, 2 and 3. All results were estimated using the preferred specification from the baseline result, with individual fixed effects regression and a vector of covariates, except without the lag of the unaffordable housing dummy, in order to observe how the average effect of unaffordable housing on mental health changes when individuals spend longer in unaffordable housing (as opposed to the effect of entering into unaffordable housing on mental health). This small change explains the difference between the coefficient in the first column of Table 3 and the

coefficient from my preferred specification from the baseline result in Table 2, as the estimation and treatment group are otherwise identical.

Table 3: Results by number of consecutive years in unaffordable housing, SF-12 MCS

	SF-12 MCS score			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
In unaffordable housing	-0.558 ^{***} (0.204)	-0.617 ^{**} (0.261)	-1.104 ^{**} (0.445)	-0.511 (0.393)
Observations	79,176	74,646	72,865	74,625
Maximum number of consecutive waves in unaffordable housing	>0	1	2	>2

Notes: This table explores how the effect of being in unaffordable housing on individuals' mental health varies with the number of consecutive years spent in unaffordable housing. All estimates are obtained using the preferred specification bar the lag of the unaffordable housing dummy. The table presents estimates of coefficient β from equation (1) with the SF-12 Mental Component Summary score as the outcome variable for four different treatment groups. In the first column, the treatment group includes all individuals who spent at least one year in unaffordable housing; in the second column, the treated are those who spent a maximum of one consecutive wave in unaffordable housing during the sampling period. Similarly, the treated in the third column spent a maximum of two consecutive waves in unaffordable housing and a maximum of at least 3 consecutive waves in unaffordable housing in the fourth column. Standard errors in brackets are clustered at primary sampling unit level and ^{***} $p < 0.01$, ^{**} $p < 0.05$. Further specifications are included in Table A.5.

In the second column, the treatment group is limited to the individuals in group 1; in the third column, to group 2; and the fourth column, to group 3. Each treatment group is compared to the control group consisting of individuals who never entered unaffordable housing.

The coefficient in the first column gives the effect of being in unaffordable housing on mental health averaged across all individuals and all years. The magnitude of this effect changes when considering more specific treatment groups. The estimates in the other columns show that the negative effect of being in unaffordable housing on mental health is above average for those who stay in unaffordable housing for a maximum of both one and two consecutive years. For those in group 2, the average impact on mental health for each of the (up to) two years they spent in unaffordable housing was of -1.104, almost double the average impact. This average impact became insignificant (at the 5% level) for those who spent at least two waves in unaffordable housing (despite a greater sample size than group 2), as well as those who spent a maximum of three waves in unaffordable housing (see Table A.3), indicating that there's a lessening impact of unaffordable housing on mental health after two consecutive waves.

Referring back to the descriptive results, it is likely that those who remain in unaffordable housing for more extended periods of time are affected by other precarious circumstances.

The robustness of these results is tested by using the difference-in-difference event-study estimator from de Chaisemartin and D’Haultfœuille (2024) that can be used with a binary and staggered treatment in the *did_multiplegt_dyn* Stata package. This estimator, depending on no-anticipation and parallel trends assumptions, allows for dynamic effects (when the outcome is affected by past treatments) and for the current or lagged treatment to have heterogeneous effects across individuals or over time, building on de Chaisemartin and D’Haultfœuille’s (2020) original work.

Event-study effects are averages, across all who enter unaffordable housing, of the effect of having received their actual rather than their period-one treatment dose, for l periods; in other words, the average effects of being exposed to a weakly higher treatment dose for l periods (de Chaisemartin and D’Haultfœuille, 2024). The estimates for this estimator, presented in Table 4, can be interpreted in a similar manner to those estimated in Table 3 but are able to account for the presence of year-specific influences on all individuals’ mental health and housing affordability, as well as heterogeneity in the treatment effect. The coefficient on a placebo, used to test the parallel trends and no-anticipation assumptions in line with recommendations from de Chaisemartin and D’Haultfœuille (2024), is found to be insignificant at the 5% level, allowing the assumptions to hold.

Table 4: Event-study effects, SF-12 MCS score

	SF-12 MCS score			
	Point estimate	Standard error	Lower bound 95% CI	Upper bound 95% CI
Effect 1	-0.732	0.289	-1.299	-0.166
Effect 2	-1.143	0.401	-1.929	-0.358
Effect 3	-0.644	0.472	-1.569	0.281

Notes: This table presents estimates of the difference-in-difference event-study estimators from de Chaisemartin and D’Haultfœuille (2024) for each of the first three years individuals spend in unaffordable housing. The outcome variable is the SF-12 Mental Component Summary score. All control variables are included bar the lag of the unaffordable housing dummy. CI refers to confidence intervals.

The coefficients for groups 1, 2 and 3 in Table 3 to the coefficients for effects 1, 2 and 3 in Table 4 yield similar conclusions but are not directly comparable. The event-study estimator

for effect 1 is able to isolate the effect on mental health of spending one wave in unaffordable housing across all individuals who spent at least one wave in unaffordable housing, regardless of whether they spent more waves in unaffordable housing afterwards. In contrast, the coefficient for group 1 isolates the effect of unaffordable housing on mental health among individuals who spent a maximum of one wave in unaffordable housing. A similar line of reasoning follows for the other groups.

The results from Table 4 concur with those from Table 3 in that the association between unaffordable housing on mental health is highest during the second consecutive year spent in unaffordable housing and becomes insignificant (at the 5% level) from the third consecutive year on. Effects 1 and 2 are of a similar magnitude to the coefficients for groups 1 and 2, suggesting that the effect of treatment effect heterogeneity and year-specific shocks on the estimates in Table 3 (and likely the baseline results that use a similar specification as well) are minimal.

Furthermore, the baseline and longitudinal results align themselves with Baker and coauthors' (2020) findings. As noted earlier, they find a similar proportion of individuals in unaffordable housing in their Australian sample when using the 30/40 rule. Their longitudinal analysis finds that the mental health of those who experienced prolonged (intermittent) exposure to unaffordable housing was 1.338 (0.515) points lower than those who never experienced unaffordable housing.

D. Variation by definition of unaffordable housing

To explore how the effect of entering unaffordable housing on mental health depends on how unaffordable housing is defined, two further definitions, as defined in the 'Treatment variables' section, are considered alongside the 30/40 rule: the 30/60m rule and the residual approach. The 30/60m rule considers those who spend more than 30% of their income on housing costs and whose income is below 60% of the national median income. The residual approach considers income after housing costs against the MIS.

The residual approach gives the broadest definition of unaffordable housing but using it limits the sample (see Table 5) to the 11 most common household types due to how the MIS is constructed. It defines 0.83 times more individuals as being in unaffordable housing than the 30/40 rule and 1.47 times the individuals as the 30/60m rule.

Table 5: Sample frequencies by definition of unaffordable housing

	30/40 rule		30/60m rule		Residual	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Total sample observations	268,233		268,233		192,134	
Observations in unaffordable housing	20,715	7.72	12,181	4.54	57,504	29.93
Total sample individuals	27,894		27,894		23,659	
Individuals in unaffordable housing at least once	7,929	28.43	5,863	21.02	14,503	61.30

Notes: This table presents sample frequencies by different definitions of unaffordable housing. The last row of the table shows the prevalence of individuals who were in unaffordable housing at least once during the sampling period.

The characteristics of the individuals in unaffordable housing according to each definition are summarised in Table A.6. Those in unaffordable housing according to the 30/40 rule are similar in many ways to those that fall under the 30/60m rule, with 59% of the observations of the former falling into the latter. Those under the 30/60m rule are less likely to be employed and more likely to be unemployed, as well as slightly more likely to be in social housing compared to other tenures, relative to those under the 30/40 rule. The biggest compositional differences exist between those in residual unaffordable housing compared to the 30/40 and 30/60m definitions. Those in the latter groups were much more likely to be unemployed; separated, divorced or widowed; to have never married; have changed residence in the last year; be from an ethnic minority background; or live in either social housing or the private rental sector.

Table 6 presents estimates of β in equation (1) on the SF-12 MCS score for those who were in unaffordable housing according to the 30/40 rule in the first column, 30/60m rule in the second column and residual approach in the third. All results were estimated using the preferred specification from the baseline result, with individual fixed effects regression and a vector of covariates included.

Table 6: Results by definition of unaffordable housing, SF-12 MCS score

	SF-12 MCS score		
	30/40 rule (1)	30/60m rule (2)	Residual (3)
In unaffordable housing	-0.567*** (0.201)	-0.615** (0.258)	-0.233 (0.160)
Observations	79,176	79,176	57,566

Notes: This table explores how the effect of being in unaffordable housing on individuals' mental health varies with the definition of unaffordable housing. It presents estimates of coefficient β from equation (1) using the preferred specification with the SF-12 Mental Component Summary score as the outcome variable. Columns 1 and 2 estimate equation (1) with an unaffordable housing dummy defined by the 30/40 and 30/60m rules, respectively. Both are ratio approaches to defining unaffordable housing. Column 3 adopts the residual approach of defining unaffordable housing. Standard errors in brackets are clustered at primary sampling unit level and *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$.

The coefficient in the first column gives the baseline result from my preferred specification. Entering 30/60m unaffordable housing is associated with a decrease in individuals' mental health score of 0.615 points relative to remaining in affordable housing, an average decrease of 0.048 points of greater magnitude than that associated with the 30/40 rule. These coefficients are not different from each other in statistically significant terms, suggesting that little treatment effect heterogeneity exists that is driven by level of income. The coefficient for the residual definition of unaffordable housing is not significant, likely because the particular approach adopted using the MIS gave quite a broad definition of unaffordable housing. These findings indicate that the 30/40 rule is a stronger measure of being in true housing affordability stress.

E. Limitations

There are limitations to the analysis carried out. First, the data does not capture variation in unaffordable housing or mental health between waves, so it is assumed that the time of year an individual was interviewed in was not systematically related to the outcome and treatment variables. Including interview month dummies as control variables suggested that this had no effect on the coefficient of interest. It is also assumed that there was no anticipation effect of entering unaffordable housing, where individuals pre-empt the effects of entering into housing unaffordability during a time of anticipated hardship, leading their level of mental health to fall before they are recorded as being in unaffordable housing. However, placebo tests using de Chaisemartin and D'Haultfoeuille's (2024) estimator suggests that the effect of anticipation effects is insignificant.

The 30/40 approach of defining unaffordable housing is imperfect. While widely adopted, it is ultimately a binary measure that attempts to capture a spectrum of housing situations. Ultimately, it was shown to be a stronger indicator of unaffordable housing than the residual approach using MIS and to provide similar results to the 30/60m approach that uses an alternative income threshold. Entering unaffordable housing according to the 30/40 rule may reflect a household beginning to pay more than 30% of their income on housing costs or a household's income falling below the 40th income percentile threshold. To mitigate against whether it was housing or low income driving the mental health effects, a transformed equivalised income variable was included as a control.

While a number of control variables were considered and included that are related to both mental health and unaffordable housing, it is possible that, despite the considerable measures taken, the analysis may suffer from bias from omitted variables or reverse causality. For example, the lagged binary indicators for depression that were considered for inclusion as covariates to account for pre-existing mental health conditions did not have an effect on the coefficient of interest. However, if these variables did not fully capture the presence of pre-existing mental health conditions, biases from reverse causality may remain.

Finally, the analysis and conclusions from this paper would be well complemented by analysis of qualitative data sources to provide more insights about the mechanisms by which unaffordable housing affects mental health.

V. Conclusion

Given the significant recent increases in mortgage and rent payments and corresponding arrears, the issue of housing affordability is particularly relevant (Bank of England, 2024; ONS, 2023b). In this paper, a small but significant association between entering unaffordable housing and mental health was found using fixed effects estimation of UK longitudinal data. The evidence also suggests that this association was greatest after spending two consecutive waves in unaffordable housing, becoming insignificant thereafter.

The findings in this paper suggest a possible causal effect of unaffordable housing on mental health, highlighting the importance of future investigation that exploits other identification strategies to add further robustness to these results.

The increase in the proportion of the population suffering from depressive disorders associated with entering unaffordable housing is estimated to result in an additional cost of at least £2.28 billion in England. This result uses estimates of the service costs and costs of lost employment of depression from McCrone et al. (2008), adjusted by Consumer Price Inflation and average weekly earnings, respectively, and is likely to underestimate the true cost of depression as it does not include costs of informal care, public service or lost productivity².

This analysis has important implications for understanding the costs and benefits of interventions to improve housing affordability and reduce inequalities in mental health. It is up to policymakers and future research to decide how the negative impact of unaffordable housing will be alleviated.

² This estimate should be interpreted with caution as it relies on strong assumptions including that (i) the share of the population that suffers from depression is the same as in 2014 and (ii) the percentage change in the share of the population that suffers from 30-day depression as predicted by the SF-12 MCS cut-off due to entering unaffordable housing is the same as the percentage change in the true share of the population that suffers from depression due to entering unaffordable housing.

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Appendix

Table A.1a: Summary statistics by affordability of housing (continued on next page)

Variable	In unaffordable housing		In affordable housing	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
SF-12 MCS score ^a	46.07	(11.51)	49.29	(9.94)
SF-12 PCS score ^b	49.05	(11.37)	50.39	(10.31)
Monthly equivalised household disposable income	847.94	(371.71)	2050.92	(2,584.52)
Household size	2.44	(1.46)	2.85	(1.39)
Number of adults	1.77	(0.99)	2.32	(1.11)
Number of children ^c	0.67	(1.02)	0.53	(0.94)

Notes: Table is continued on the next page. This table presents sample summary statistics by whether an individual's housing was affordable. Figures are estimated using the unweighted pooled analytical sample.

^a MCS is Mental Component Summary.

^b PCS is Physical Component Summary.

^c Number of children refers to number of own dependent children in the household according to the Department for Work and Pension's definition.

Table A.1b: Summary statistics by affordability of housing (cont.)

Variable	In unaffordable housing		In affordable housing	
	Mean	n	Mean	n
Labour force status				
Employed	0.51	10,560	0.62	153,404
Unemployed	0.13	2,692	0.03	7,423
Economically inactive	0.37	7,661	0.36	89,073
Age cohort				
16-24	0.14	2,900	0.09	22,276
25-34	0.18	3,729	0.13	32,177
35-44	0.22	4,557	0.17	42,078
45-54	0.20	4,143	0.21	51,978
55-64	0.15	3,107	0.20	49,503
65+	0.10	2,072	0.20	49,503
Sex				
Male	0.39	8,079	0.44	108,908
Female	0.61	12,636	0.56	138,610
Education: has a degree	0.22	4,557	0.31	76,731
Ethnic group				
White	0.76	15,741	0.88	217,758
Asian	0.12	2,485	0.07	17,322
Black	0.07	1,450	0.02	4,949
Mixed/multiple ethnic groups	0.03	621	0.02	4,949
Other	0.01	207	0.00	0
Marital status				
Married/de facto	0.44	9,074	0.70	172,926
Sep./widow./divorced	0.23	4,743	0.12	29,644
Never married	0.33	6,805	0.18	44,467
Long-standing health condition or disability	0.36	7,457	0.33	81,681
Changed address in the last year	0.12	2,163	0.05	10,982
Would prefer to move house	0.37	7,665	0.29	71,780
Housing tenure				
Owned	0.00	0	0.40	98,516
Owned mortgage	0.35	7,239	0.42	103,442
Social rented	0.32	6,619	0.10	24,629
Private rented	0.32	6,619	0.07	17,240
Other	0.02	414	0.01	2,463

Notes: This table presents sample summary statistics by whether an individual's housing was affordable. Figures are estimated using the unweighted pooled analytical sample.

Table A.2: Baseline result including controls, SF-12 MCS score

	SF-12 MCS score	
	Coefficient	SD
In unaffordable housing	-0.567 ***	(0.201)
In unaffordable housing ($t - 1$)	0.035	(0.196)
SF-12 MCS score ($t - 1$)	0.110 ***	(0.007)
Monthly equivalised household income ^a	-0.029	(0.095)
Labour force status ^b		
Unemployed	-1.583 ***	(0.364)
Economically inactive	-1.050 ***	(0.197)
Household size	-0.017	(0.114)
Number of adults	-0.031	(0.120)
Age	-0.607 ***	(0.059)
Age squared	0.002 ***	(0.000)
Changed address in the last year	0.088	(0.194)
SF-12 PCS score	-0.355 ***	(0.009)
Regional unemployment rate	-0.190 ***	(0.038)
Marital status ^c		
Sep/widow/divorced	-1.059 ***	(0.281)
Never married	-1.024 ***	(0.369)
Housing tenure ^d		
Owned mortgage	-0.608 ***	(0.176)
Social rented	-1.144 **	(0.501)
Private rented	-0.903 ***	(0.322)
Other	-0.888	(0.549)

Notes: This table explores the effect of entering unaffordable housing on individuals' mental health. It presents the complete results from the preferred specification in Table 2 that estimates coefficient β from equation (1) with the SF-12 Mental Component Summary score as the outcome variable. Standard errors in brackets are clustered at primary sampling unit level and *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$.

^a Refers to the inverse hyperbolic sine of monthly equivalised household disposable income.

^b Base category is "Employed".

^c Base category is "Married/de facto".

^d Base category is "Owned".

Table A.3: Effects on predicted incidence of depression in the population

	36.76 ≤ SF-12 MCS	40.60 ≤ SF-12 MCS
	(1)	(2)
In unaffordable housing	0.021*** (0.008)	0.008 (0.009)
Observations	79,176	79,176

Notes: This table explores the effect of entering unaffordable housing on the share of the population who have a depressive disorder. It presents estimates of coefficient β from equation (1), where the outcome variable is the share of the population who have SF-12 MCS scores below thresholds indicative of depressive disorders. The estimate in the first column reflects the percentage point change in the share of the population with 30-day depressive disorders and the estimate in the second column reflects the equivalent change in the share of the population with 12-month depressive disorders. Standard errors in brackets are clustered at primary sampling unit level and *** $p < 0.01$.

Table A.4a: Summary statistics by number of consecutive years in unaffordable housing (cont. on next page)

Variable	Maximum of 1 consecutive year in unaffordable housing		Maximum of 2 consecutive years in unaffordable housing		Maximum of at least 3 years in unaffordable housing	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
SF-12 MCS score ^a	46.26	(11.30)	45.98	(11.55)	45.95	(11.67)
SF-12 PCS score ^b	50.01	(11.08)	49.44	(11.17)	48.01	(11.63)
Monthly equivalised household disposable income	831.88	(391.78)	856.51	(369.77)	858.32	(353.21)
Household size	2.78	(1.52)	2.48	(1.38)	2.11	(1.36)
Number of adults	2.04	(1.15)	1.79	(0.89)	1.53	(0.81)
Number of children ^c	0.75	(1.05)	0.69	(1.03)	0.58	(0.97)
Age	41.43	(15.14)	41.95	(15.84)	47.18	(16.44)

Notes: Table is continued below. This table presents sample summary statistics by the maximum number of consecutive waves an individual spent in unaffordable housing. Figures are estimated using the unweighted pooled analytical sample.

^a MCS is Mental Component Summary.

^b PCS is Physical Component Summary.

^c Number of children refers to number of own dependent children in the household according to the Department for Work and Pension's definition.

Table A.4b: Summary statistics by number of consecutive years in unaffordable housing (cont.)

Variable	Maximum of 1 consecutive year in unaffordable housing		Maximum of 2 consecutive years in unaffordable housing		Maximum of at least 3 years in unaffordable housing	
	Mean	n	Mean	n	Mean	n
In unaffordable housing	1.00	7,850	1.00	4,118	1.00	8,747
Labour force status						
Employed	0.57	4,473	0.54	2,223	0.44	3,846
Unemployed	0.11	863	0.12	494	0.14	1,224
Economically inactive	0.32	2,511	0.35	1,441	0.42	3,671
Age cohort						
16-24	0.15	1,178	0.18	741	0.11	962
25-34	0.21	1,649	0.18	741	0.15	1,312
35-44	0.23	1,806	0.22	906	0.21	1,837
45-54	0.20	1,570	0.20	824	0.21	1,837
55-64	0.12	942	0.14	577	0.18	1,574
65+	0.07	550	0.08	329	0.14	1,225
Sex						
Male	0.40	3,140	0.38	1,565	0.39	3,411
Female	0.60	4,710	0.62	2,553	0.61	5,336
Education: has a degree	0.26	2,041	0.24	988	0.18	1,574
Ethnic group						
White	0.76	5,964	0.76	3,130	0.77	6,735
Asian	0.14	1,099	0.13	535	0.11	962
Black	0.06	471	0.07	288	0.08	700
Mixed/multiple ethnic group	0.03	235	0.03	124	0.03	262
Other	0.01	78	0.01	41	0.01	87
Marital status						
Married/de facto	0.54	4,216	0.47	1,928	0.33	2,875
Sep./widow./divorced	0.17	1,327	0.19	779	0.31	2,701
Never married	0.29	2,264	0.34	1,395	0.37	3,224
Long-standing health condition or disability	0.32	2,512	0.34	1,400	0.41	3,586
Changed address in the last year	0.13	858	0.14	496	0.11	866
Would prefer to move house	0.36	2,826	0.37	1,524	0.37	3,236
Housing tenure						
Owned	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0
Owned mortgage	0.45	3,525	0.37	1,521	0.24	2,097
Social rented	0.27	2,115	0.30	1,234	0.37	3,233
Private rented	0.26	2,037	0.32	1,316	0.37	3,233
Other	0.02	157	0.02	82	0.02	175

Notes: This table presents sample summary statistics by the maximum number of consecutive waves an individual spent in unaffordable housing. Figures are estimated using the unweighted pooled analytical sample.

Table A.5: Additional results by number of consecutive years of unaffordable housing, SF-12 MCS score

	SF-12 MCS score						
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
In unaffordable housing	-0.558*** (0.204)	-0.617** (0.261)	-0.615** (0.300)	-1.104** (0.445)	-0.511 (0.393)	-0.727 (0.607)	-0.379 (0.507)
Observations	79,176	74,646	76,010	72,865	74,625	72,379	73,726
Maximum number of consecutive waves in unaffordable housing	>0	1	>1	2	>2	3	>3

Notes: This table explores how the effect of being in unaffordable housing on individuals' mental health varies with the number of consecutive years spent in unaffordable housing. All estimates are obtained using the preferred specification bar the lag of the unaffordable housing dummy. The table presents estimates of coefficient β from equation (1) with the SF-12 Mental Component Summary score as the outcome variable for seven different treatment groups. In the first column, the treatment group includes all individuals who spent at least one year in unaffordable housing; in the second column, the treated are those who spent a maximum of one consecutive year in unaffordable housing during the sampling period. Similarly, the treated in the third column spent a maximum of at least two consecutive years in unaffordable housing, a maximum of two consecutive years in unaffordable housing in the fourth column, a maximum of at least three consecutive years in unaffordable housing in the fifth column, a maximum of three consecutive years in the sixth column and a maximum of at least four years in unaffordable housing in the seventh column. Standard errors in brackets are clustered at primary sampling unit level and *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$.

Table A.6a: Summary statistics by definition of unaffordable housing (cont. on next page)

Variable	30/40 rule		30/60m rule		Residual	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
SF-12 MCS score ^a	46.07	(11.51)	45.51	(11.80)	47.13	(10.80)
SF-12 PCS score ^b	49.05	(11.37)	48.96	(11.31)	50.10	(10.65)
Monthly equivalised household income ^c	847.94	(371.71)	611.53	(278.85)	1036.25	(430.87)
Household size	2.44	(1.46)	2.53	(1.50)	2.95	(1.40)
Number of adults	1.77	(0.99)	1.84	(1.05)	1.74	(0.58)
Number of children ^d	0.67	(1.02)	0.70	(1.04)	1.21	(1.16)

Notes: Table is continued on the next page. This table presents sample summary statistics by definition of unaffordable housing. Figures are estimated using the unweighted pooled analytical sample.

^a MCS is Mental Component Summary.

^b PCS is Physical Component Summary.

^c Refers to monthly equivalised household disposable income.

^d Number of children refers to number of own dependent children in the household according to the Department for Work and Pension's definition.

Table A.6b: Summary statistics by definition of unaffordable housing (cont.)

Variable	30/40 rule		30/60m rule		Residual	
	Mean	n	Mean	n	Mean	n
In unaffordable housing	1.00	20,715	1.00	12,181	0.30	17,173
Labour force status						
Employed	0.51	10,560	0.43	5,234	0.60	34,492
Unemployed	0.13	2,692	0.18	2,191	0.07	4,024
Economically inactive	0.37	7,661	0.39	4,747	0.33	18,970
Age cohort						
16-24	0.14	2,900	0.16	1,949	0.07	4,025
25-34	0.18	3,729	0.17	2,071	0.22	12,651
35-44	0.22	4,557	0.22	2,680	0.30	17,251
45-54	0.20	4,143	0.22	2,680	0.18	10,351
55-64	0.15	3,107	0.15	1,827	0.12	6,900
65+	0.10	2,072	0.08	974	0.09	5,175
Sex						
Male	0.39	8,079	0.40	4,872	0.40	23,002
Female	0.61	12,636	0.60	7,309	0.60	34,502
Education: has a degree	0.22	4,557	0.19	2,314	0.24	13,801
Ethnic group						
White	0.76	15,741	0.73	8,890	0.83	47,708
Asian	0.12	2,485	0.14	1,705	0.10	5,748
Black	0.07	1,450	0.08	974	0.04	2,299
Mixed/multiple ethnic groups	0.03	621	0.03	365	0.02	1,150
Other	0.01	207	0.01	122	0.01	575
Marital status						
Married/de facto	0.44	9,074	0.44	5,329	0.66	37,888
Sep./widow./divorced	0.23	4,743	0.20	2,422	0.15	8,611
Never married	0.33	6,805	0.35	4,239	0.18	10,333
Long-standing health condition or disability	0.36	7,457	0.36	4,385	0.32	18,401
Changed address in the last year	0.12	2,163	0.12	1,275	0.09	4,511
Would prefer to move house	0.37	7,665	0.37	4,507	0.35	20,126
Housing tenure						
Owned	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.15	8,594
Owned mortgage	0.35	7,239	0.33	4,011	0.43	24,635
Social rented	0.32	6,619	0.36	4,375	0.23	13,177
Private rented	0.32	6,619	0.28	3,403	0.17	9,739
Other	0.02	414	0.02	243	0.02	1,146

Notes: This table presents sample summary statistics by definition of unaffordable housing. Figures are estimated using the unweighted pooled analytical sample.